

Optical and electrical properties of thiarubrine A simulated via the Hückel method and the nonequilibrium Green's function

Francesco Scotognella

Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy

E-mail address: francesco.scotognella@polito.it

Abstract

Thiarubrine A, a fascinating class of linear carbon chains, can be extracted from certain plants and are known for their photolabile pigment properties. In this study, a modified Hückel method to investigate the optical properties of thiarubrine A has been employed, determining its absorption spectrum and wavelength-dependent complex refractive index. Additionally, using the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism, the conductance of a single Thiarubrine A molecule has been derived. Exploiting its photolability, a light-induced switch in single-molecule conductance has been demonstrated through ultraviolet-visible irradiation, which produces a photoproduct containing a thiophene group. These findings enhance our understanding of the optical properties of naturally occurring polyynes and highlight their potential applications in single-molecule junctions for nanoelectronics.

Keywords: Polyynes; single molecule conductance; nonequilibrium Green's function.

Introduction

Linear chains of carbon atoms can exist in two idealized isomeric forms: cumulenes, characterized by consecutive double bonds ($C=C=C$) [1], and polyynes, which feature alternating single and triple bonds ($C-C\equiv C$) [2–4]. Polyynes are particularly intriguing due to their unique optical and electrical properties [5–9]. Many organisms can synthesize polyynes [10]. Among these, thiarubrines stand out as a significant class, garnering attention for their distinctive reactivity, unique biological activity, and potential medicinal applications [11,12]. Thiarubrines are red, phototoxic polyynes found in the Asteraceae family [13], notable for their high instability in light [14]. The optical properties of these polyynes can be theoretically studied using various methods, such as the Hückel method. In Hückel theory, molecular orbitals are expressed as linear combinations of atomic orbitals (LCAO). The key approximations in this theory include: i) the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, which assumes fixed nuclei positions; and ii) the representation of molecular orbitals as linear combinations of p_z orbitals, neglecting electron-electron interactions [15]. With the Hamiltonian built within the framework of the Hückel theory, it is possible to find the conductance of the single molecule via the use of the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism.

In this study, a modified Hückel method, as detailed by Solomon et al. [16], has been utilized to investigate the optical properties of thiarubrine A. Its absorption spectrum and wavelength-dependent complex refractive index have been determined. Additionally, using the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism, the conductance of a single thiarubrine A molecule has been derived. Finally, by leveraging the photolability of thiarubrine A, which produces a thiophene-containing photoproduct upon ultraviolet-visible irradiation, a light-induced switch in the single molecule's conductance has been demonstrated.

Methods

Herein, a modified Hückel method, following Solomon et al. [16] has been followed. Within this framework, the time-independent Schrödinger equation is given by:

$$H|\psi\rangle = E|\psi\rangle \quad (1)$$

With H the Hamiltonian, ψ the eigenfunction and E the eigenvalue. Subsequently, eigenvalues and eigenfunctions have been determined. In order to find the transition probabilities, the Fermi golden rule has been used:

$$\Gamma_{i \rightarrow j} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle \psi^j | H | \psi^i \rangle|^2 \quad (2)$$

The transition probabilities have been estimated between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied orbitals. Gaussian peaks have been used for the simulation of the absorption spectra. Studying the transitions from the ground state i to the different j th excited states, the absorption coefficient can be written as

$$\alpha(E) = \sum_j \Gamma_{i \rightarrow j} \exp\left(\frac{(E - (E_j - E_i))^2}{2c^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

With a linewidth c of the peaks of 0.2 eV. In order to extract from the absorption spectrum the imaginary part of the complex refractive index, the following expression has been used, modifying the one reported in [17]:

$$k(E) = \frac{A\alpha(E)}{4\pi} \quad (4)$$

With the parameter A set to 1×10^{15} . The real part of the complex refractive index can be obtained via the Kramers-Kronig relations [18]:

$$n(\bar{\nu}) - 1 = \frac{2}{\pi} \mathcal{P} \int_0^\infty \frac{\omega k(\omega)}{\omega^2 - \bar{\nu}^2} d\omega \quad (5)$$

It is noteworthy that the Kramers-Kronig relations are Hilbert transforms [19]. In the case of the real part of the refractive index a constant offset of 1.5 has been applied as in Refs. [20,21].

The complex refractive index can be thus written as

$$n(E) = n_{real}(E) + k(E) \quad (6)$$

For the calculation of the elastic transmission, the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism has been employed, following Solomon et al. [16]. Assuming that only a single site of the molecule couples to each electrode, for thiarubrine A, the vector for the left electrode is

$$V_L = [\gamma \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \quad (7)$$

While the vector for the right electrode is

$$V_R = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ \gamma \ 0 \ 0] \quad (8)$$

The value of γ is -1 eV, following Solomon et al. [16]. The broadening function is

$$\Gamma^{L(R)} = 2\pi\rho V_{L(R)}V_{L(R)}^\dagger \quad (9)$$

Where ρ is the density of state of the electrode, set to $1/2\pi$ (eV)⁻¹ (following Solomon et al. [16]). With the broadening function it is possible to determine the tunneling self-energy, which is purely imaginary,

$$\Sigma_T^{L(R)} = -\frac{i}{2}\Gamma^{L(R)} \quad (10)$$

The energy dependent retarded Green's function can be thus determined as

$$G^r(E) = (E - H_{mol} - \Sigma_T^L - \Sigma_T^R)^{-1} \quad (11)$$

The advanced Green's function $G^a(E)$ is the conjugated transpose of the retarded Green's function. With the broadening functions and the Green's functions, it is possible to determine the energy dependent elastic transmission

$$T(E) = Tr[\Gamma^L G^r(E) \Gamma^R G^a(E)] \quad (12)$$

The transmission is related to the conductance through the relation [22]

$$G = G_0 T(E_F) \quad (13)$$

G_0 is the quantum of conductance (with value $7.748 \times 10^{-5} S$).

Results and discussion

In Figure 1 the chemical formula of thiarubrine A has been drawn. In order to build the Hamiltonian in the framework of the Hückel method, a numbering of the molecule atomic site has been adopted, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of thiarubrine A. The numbering of the atomic site corresponds to the index in the Hamiltonian.

Thus, the Hamiltonian for thiarubrine A has been made in the following way:

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ b & a & bT & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & bT & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & b & a & bD & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bS & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & bD & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b & a & bD & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bD & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bS \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b & a & bT & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bT & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b & a & bT & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bT & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b & a & bD & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bD & a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & bS & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & aS & bB \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bS & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bB & aS \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

In the Hamiltonian, a is the on-site energy for carbon atoms, b is carbon-carbon single bond coupling element, bD is carbon-carbon double bond coupling element, bT is the carbon-carbon single bond coupling element, aS is the on-site energy for sulfur atoms, bB is the sulfur-sulfur single bond coupling element, bS is the carbon-sulfur single bond coupling element. Taking into account the experimental absorption spectrum of thiarubrine A [14,23], with characteristic peaks at 345 nm and 490 nm, a fair agreement is found with the parameters reported in Table 1.

Parameter	Value (eV)
a	0
b	-3
bD	-4.2
bT	-5.8
aS	-3.33
bB	-1.89
bS	-2.07

Table 1. Parameters used in the Hamiltonian used in the time-independent Schrödinger equation (Equation 1) for thiarubrine A.

The simulated absorption spectrum is depicted in Figure 2. The peaks correspond to oscillator strengths of the different electronic transitions, as described in Equation 3.

Figure 2. Absorption spectrum with peaks corresponding to oscillator strengths of the different electronic transitions for thiarubrine A (peak linewidth of 0.2 eV).

By using Equations 4 and 5, it is possible to determine the wavelength dependent complex refractive index of thiarubrine A, starting from the calculated absorption spectrum. The real part (black curve) and the imaginary part (red curve) of the refractive index is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Real part (black curve) of the imaginary part (red curve) of the refractive index of thiarubrine A.

By employing the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism it is possible to determine the elastic transmission of thiarubrine A (Equation 12).

Figure 4. Transmission spectrum of thiarubrine A.

Setting the Fermi energy at 0 eV, the conductance of the molecule is $1.35 \mu\text{S}$ (Equation 13). Upon light irradiation, thiarubrine A is converted to a photoproduct thiophene A, depicted in Figure 5 [14].

Figure 5. Chemical structure of thiophene A. The numbering of the atomic site corresponds to the index in the Hamiltonian.

The Hamiltonian H' related to the photoproduct thiophene A can be written in the following way

$$H' = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ b & a & bT & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & bT & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & b & a & bD & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bS \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & bD & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b & a & bD & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bD & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bS \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b & a & bT & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bT & a & b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b & a & bT & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bT & a & b & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & b & a & bD & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & bD & a & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & bS & 0 & 0 & bS & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & aS \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

The values of the parameters used in the Hamiltonian H' for thiophene A are the same ones of the Hamiltonian H for thiarubrine A. For thiophene A, the conductance, calculated using Equation 13, is 0.56 μS . Thus, a light induced variation of the electrical behavior can be achieved in the presented molecular system.

Conclusion

In this work the optical and electric properties of the molecule thiarubrine A has been simulated by using a modified Hückel method (exhaustively described in Ref. [16]) and the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism. The simulated absorption spectrum has been determined and, by choosing the proper parameters in the Hamiltonian, a good matching with the experimental data can be found. From the simulated absorption spectrum, it is possible to derive the wavelength dependent complex refractive index. Moreover, with the employment of the nonequilibrium Green's function formalism, the conductance of the single molecule has been found. Taking into account the photolability of thiarubrine A, via light irradiation a change of conductance can be achieved. Such findings can be interesting for the understanding of the optical properties of polyynes occurring in nature and for their exploitation in nanoelectronics.

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